

EARTH MOON EDUCATION CUBESATS AND PAYLOAD FOR RESEARCH AND TRAINING

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Summary: We have developed cubesat and shoebox-size payload (CSP4X) for lunar and planetary exploration. The Earth Moon Education CubeSats (EMECS) project includes the design and implementation of a 3U CubeSat aimed at remote sensing of Earth and the Moon.

This project represents a significant educational opportunity for workforce development, and for students to engage in hands-on engineering and scientific research.

Cubesat shoebox payload (CSP4X) for exploration

We have tested various instruments for remote sensing and sample analysis. These include multi-band cameras, spectrometers and Raman.

They were tested using samples from meteorites (Moon, Mars, asteroids), analogue field samples from EuroMoonMars campaigns (Leiden, HI-SEAS, Iceland, Vulcano, Etna). We conducted also instruments validation inside ExoSpaceHab-X Moon lab and other MoonMars base analogues. The miniaturised instruments were also adapted to telescopes to observe the Moon and celestial targets.

Cubesat or shoebox-size payload can be developed for future lunar and planetary opportunities. We have tested the operations of such payload on ExoGeoLab lander used in previous EuroMoonMars simulation and field campaigns. We have also developed some simulations of mixtures of ice, minerals and organics that could be relevant for MoonMars polar regions, as well as outer planet icy Moons. We developed a concept specific shoe-box system for extracting organics from icy Moons such as Enceladus, or galilean Moons.

The ExoGeoLab lander has been tested earlier in volcanic, desertic and glacial environments. We are planning to adapt the ExoGeoLab lander to other planetary analogue environments to validate the accommodation of instruments for sample analysis, environment measurements and telescopic remote sensing.

Missions, Data, Instruments, Field Work, Astronauts:

EuroMoonMars is an ILEWG programme [1-235] in collaboration with space agencies, academia, universities and research institutions and industries. The programme includes

research activities supporting Moon and Mars Missions for data analysis, instruments tests and development, field tests in MoonMars analogue, pilot projects, training and hands-on workshops, technical visits and outreach activities.

Earth Moon Education CubeSats (EMECS)

This programme includes the design and implementation of a 3U CubeSat aimed at remote sensing of Earth and the Moon. The CubeSat will carry advanced imaging and spectrometric instruments to gather data for scientific research and technology demonstration. The mission objectives include monitoring environmental changes on Earth and analyzing the lunar surface composition. The proposed mission will contribute to our understanding of these celestial bodies and advance CubeSat technology for future space missions. Deploying our CubeSat on a lunar lander presents unique scientific and exploratory opportunities. The Moon serves as a valuable platform for scientific research, enabling a range of investigations that enhance our understanding of lunar geology and resources. A primary objective of the CubeSat mission is to analyze the lunar regolith, the layer of loose, fragmented material covering solid bedrock. This investigation will focus on several key aspects: first, using spectrometric instruments to analyze the mineralogical composition of the regolith; second, identifying valuable resources within the regolith, such as water ice and hydrogen, which could inform future lunar exploration strategies; and third, utilizing the data collected on regolith composition to aid in planning future sample return missions.

The primary goals of this group project developed by LUNEX EuroMoonMars with students and supervisors from Leiden Observatory, Leiden LIACS computer science, LiS Leiden Instrument School, TU Delft, In Holland, LV Fotonika include:

1. Develop a CubeSat for Earth Orbit and Lunar Lander: The Education CubeSat will be designed for 3 successive applications: EMECS1 to operate in Earth orbit;

EMECS2 to operate in lunar orbit; EMECS3 equipped with wheels for mobility to be brought by a lander on the Moon.

The CubeSat will utilize multi-band imaging capabilities, potentially including a spectrometer, to collect data on environmental changes, vegetation health on Earth, and mineral resources.

2. Create a Functional Tabletop Prototype: by spring 2025, we aim to start developing a functional tabletop version of the CubeSat to demonstrate core functionalities

3. Focus on Payload Systems: Our emphasis will be on designing payload systems that target a 3U configuration, including cameras (Figure 2) and an onboard computer.

Onboard Computer. Initially, we will use a laptop on the table as an onboard computer to run simulations and manage data collection. This setup will allow us to develop and test software applications necessary for operating the CubeSat's payload systems. Once the software is validated, we will transition to a more compact onboard computer solution for the final design.

Frame Structure Design Prototyping. The structural design of the CubeSat will commence with CAD software. Students will create detailed models of the CubeSat frame, ensuring that it meets the necessary specifications for strength, weight, and thermal management.

To facilitate rapid prototyping, alternatively we can use a 3D printer to create a physical model of the CubeSat frame. This prototype will help us evaluate the design's feasibility and make any necessary adjustments before moving to final assembly.

Timeline. After a first phase of definition and team forming since september 2025, the EMECS group project second phase will span 20 weeks, starting from February 15. Dr M. Raouf is daily supervisor, and Prof Foing is co-supervisor and funding customer with LUNEX foundation. The detailed timeline is as follows:

Month	Tasks
Sept	Definition of project and hiring manager
Oct	Consolidation and call for students
November	Call for students
December	Interviews and tasks allocation
January	Confirmation of EMECS students team
February	Start EMECS group project
March	Develop tabletop functional version
April	Develop payload CubeSat
April 15	Procure bus CubeSat kits
May	Assembly and lab testing
May 15	Field tests (remote sensing)
June	Completion, presentation, and report

July Consolidation of results with master students
Follow-Up Phase

After June, we will enter a follow-up phase lasting 20 weeks until December 2025. This phase will involve:

- Designing an Earth Observation (EO) CubeSat
- Designing a CubeSat for a rover on a lunar lander
- Submitting the designs to the ESA Academy for space qualifications

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References: [235]: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/search/q=euromoonmars%20or%20eurogeomars%20or%20ilewg>